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A cost-benefit analysis for PID implementation in Czechia

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Acknowledgements

Authors

Dr Phill Jones (lead author), <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0525-6323>

Josh Brown, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8689-4935>

Alice Meadows, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2161-3781>

Fiona Murphy, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1693-1240>

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Executive Summary

As part of CARDS (Czech Academic and Research Discovery Services) project¹, the Czech National Library of Technology (NTK) commissioned MoreBrains Cooperative to provide a cost-benefit analysis of implementation of selected persistent identifiers (PIDs) in Czech information systems in research, development and innovation.

Persistent identifiers provide a long-lasting and unique digital reference to an entity. Entities that are integral to the research, development, and innovation system include organisations (universities, funders, facilities, etc.), people who contribute to research (as researchers, technicians, administrators, authors, reviewers, etc.), instruments, equipment, projects, grants, and research outputs. PIDs can link to the entity itself (if it is a digital object), or to a web page that provides access to and information about the entity, or they can provide access to descriptive metadata about the entity.

The purpose of the analysis is threefold:

1. to independently evaluate and quantify current usage of selected PIDs in the Czech Research & Development (R&D) environment as of 2024;
2. to assess the potential benefit of further expanding the use of PIDs compared to the cost of centralised financial, administrative, and methodological support for their use via the CARDS project;
3. in four years' time (2028), to revisit the cost-benefit analysis, determine what progress has been made, and formulate further plans and strategies for supporting PIDs after the completion of the CARDS project.

This report addresses the first two of these objectives by quantifying the current PID landscape in Czechia. Between its publication and the 2028 re-run of the analysis, a series of surveys and outreach initiatives will be conducted, which will then feed into the final output.

There are many potential benefits of digital technologies in research, development, and innovation, with efficiency often cited as a prime benefit of the digitalisation of processes. However, evidence shows that the administrative burden on researchers is as high as it has ever been [1]. Our research has shown that the information systems used in research organisations are often siloed, and manual data entry is frequently repeated across systems [2].

This reality is officially recognised as an issue for Czech research. The National Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization of the Czech Republic 2021 - 2027 (the RIS3 strategy) states that “Outdated legislation and a high administrative burden across the entire R&D system are... a problem.” [3]

To address this, the National Research, Development and Innovation Policy of the Czech Republic 2021+ (RDI strategy) cites the need to “cut RDI bureaucracy, mainly when project proposals are filed and costs are reported and billed on the basis of the same rules for all providers” [4]. In addition, the Innovation Strategy of the Czech Republic 2019-2030 contains a priority to “avoid the

¹ More details about the Czech Academic and Research Discovery Services (CARDS) project can be found here: <https://www.techlib.cz/en/84940-czech-academic-and-research-discovery-services-cards>.

obligation to re-provide information already submitted earlier.” [5] The methodology used to calculate the benefits of PIDs focuses on the reuse of metadata, and the time savings and efficiencies that this can generate, so it aligns closely with these ambitions. Other national policy priorities that are served by increased PID adoption include the push to more open research, the development of the Czech knowledge economy, and increasing the impact and social relevance of research.

Our analysis shows that, by reusing metadata from PID registries for three key entities (publications, projects and funding grants), the potential overall financial savings from metadata re-use and process automation are higher than the financial costs of PID integrations and support. Our modelling indicates that **the time savings from PID adoption could be as high as 7,207 person days per year, which would equate to net savings of 13,214,713 CZK.**

In addition to the cost savings generated by PIDs and the support services provided by the CARDS project, the **ORCID and DataCite consortia, started as part of the national PIDs support programme led by NTK, also save money.** We compare the costs of individual memberships to the consortia fees and find that, at current membership levels, **the savings for Czech institutions from these two consortia combined is 3,050,240 CZK annually.**

Delivering these benefits relies on the use of PIDs, and the integration of PID Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) into various systems used for research management. This enables the metadata associated with PIDs to be reused in everyday workflows and, as new entities are created, information about them can be captured as metadata associated with a PID and shared for subsequent reuse. We therefore offer a series of recommendations to maximise both PID adoption and evidence of future benefits. These are:

- **Undertake follow-up research – to survey number and scope of current and planned PID integrations within Czech institutions and to evaluate the coverage of Czech research entities within PID registries.** This will establish a baseline of PID adoption and enable ongoing assessment of progress;
- **Set a medium to longer term target of 80% coverage across all five priority PIDs, reinforced with a target of 60% institutional system integration of PIDs** (calculated either in absolute terms – number of systems – or in terms of systems containing 60% of the overall research information) as to ensure a good return on investment in PID adoption;
- **Promote the value of PIDs to Czech institutions and researchers to maximise adoption and coverage of key priority PIDs;**
- **Increase the visibility of Czech research in global PID registries** to maximise discoverability, reach, and impact to support the delivery of the goals of the key Czech national research and development strategies to increase the international visibility and attractiveness of Czech research;
- **Implement PIDs in shared national systems**, such as IS VaVal, National Repository, and other national systems and services. This will ensure that smaller organisations – those that lack technical capacity and those with a lower volume of research activity – can also benefit from PIDs directly, share information about their activities more widely, and ensure that their contributions to the growth of the Czech knowledge economy are efficient and effective;

- **Undertake additional research to identify keystone systems in which research information is aggregated** (such as funder grant applications, reporting platforms, etc.) and target them for priority PID integrations. This will both increase the volume of metadata available for re-use via PID registries and also enhance the effectiveness of shared services.

Even allowing for the conservative assumptions used throughout this analysis, it is clear that the benefits of PID adoption in Czechia are significant. The real-world benefits are likely to exceed the levels estimated in this report, but will require targeted, strategic investment and focused support to be realised. This investment and support should be considered in the design of future national strategies and implementation plans. A mixed approach that includes central services, longer-term technical support, community education, and engagement will support an equitable and efficient rollout of PIDs in Czechia. This should be underpinned by robust evidence of adoption levels and current information-gathering burdens or inefficiencies in order to accurately target activities at the points of greatest need or potential impact, and to maximise the reach and scale of the Czech PID network.

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1 Introduction

The goals of the CARDS (Czech Academic and Research Discovery Services) project² are to create a central platform for managing all types of information resources for Czech research organisations and to participate in creating a common background for the implementation of data-oriented components of the Open Science strategy in the Czech Republic, primarily within the Open/FAIR Data and EOSC pillars, which includes support of PID adoption and services. As part of this project, the Czech National Library of Technology (NTK) commissioned MoreBrains Cooperative to provide a cost-benefit analysis of selected persistent identifiers (PIDs) in Czech research systems.

The purpose of the analysis is threefold: 1) to independently evaluate and quantify current usage of selected PIDs in the Czech R&D environment as of 2024; 2) to assess the potential benefit of further expanding the use of PIDs compared to the cost of centralised financial, administrative, and methodological support for their use via the CARDS project; 3) in four years' time (2028), to revisit the cost-benefit analysis, determine what progress has been made, and formulate further plans and strategies for supporting PIDs after the completion of the CARDS project.

This report addresses the first two of these objectives by quantifying the current PID landscape in Czechia. Between its publication and the 2028 re-run of the analysis, a series of surveys and outreach initiatives will be conducted, which will then feed into the final output.

2 Understanding the benefits of PIDs

Persistent identifiers provide a long-lasting and unique digital reference to an entity. Entities that are integral to the research, development, and innovation system include organisations (universities, funders, facilities, etc.), people who contribute to research (as researchers, technicians, administrators, authors, reviewers, etc.), instruments, equipment, projects, grants, and research outputs. PIDs can link to the entity itself (if it is a digital object), or to a web page that provides access to and information about the entity, or they can provide access to descriptive metadata about the entity.

In the last 30 years, research has become increasingly networked. At the same time, there has been an explosive growth in the scale of activity, the rates of publication, and the volume of data resulting from and about research. Linked digital references and reliable metadata are, therefore, now vital to the conduct and analysis of research, and PIDs are widely recognised as a fundamental component of a modern digital research system. This is evidenced by the growth in the creation of national PID strategies³, and the importance of PIDs to key policy implementation plans, such as the European Open Science Cloud [6].

² More details about the Czech Academic and Research Discovery Services (CARDS) project can be found here: <https://www.techlib.cz/en/84940-czech-academic-and-research-discovery-services-cards>.

³ More details about the National PID Strategies RDA working group can be found here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rationale/national-pid-strategies-interest-group/>.

2.1 PIDs create efficiencies

There are many potential benefits of digital technologies in research, development, and innovation, with efficiency often cited as a prime benefit of the digitalisation of processes. However, evidence shows that the administrative burden on researchers is as high as it has ever been [1]. Our research has shown that the information systems used in research organisations are often siloed, and manual data entry is frequently repeated across systems [2].

This reality is officially recognised as an issue for Czech research. The National Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization of the Czech Republic 2021 - 2027 (the RIS3 strategy) states that “Outdated legislation and a high administrative burden across the entire R&D system are... a problem.” [3]

To address this, the National Research, Development and Innovation Policy of the Czech Republic 2021+ (RDI strategy) cites the need to “cut RDI bureaucracy, mainly when project proposals are filed and costs are reported and billed on the basis of the same rules for all providers” [4] (see “Objective 1: Put in place a strategically managed and effectively funded system of research, development and innovation in the CR”). In addition, the Innovation Strategy of the Czech Republic 2019-2030 contains a priority to “avoid the obligation to re-provide information already submitted earlier.” [5]

We have shown in previous cost-benefit analyses that the re-use of metadata from PID registries can deliver significant time and cost savings for common research processes [2, 7, 8]. The national IS VaVal platform is the primary destination for research reporting in the Czech Republic, and uses a model in which efficiencies are delivered via the “reuse of data already entered once in other public administration information systems (connection to basic registers) and cooperation in sharing data initially entered into IS VaVal by other state administration bodies, changes and expansion of identifiers and content of records.” [9]

The re-use of metadata from PIDs is a valuable complement to this proven approach, enabling improvements to efficiency within institutions. These efficiencies reinforce the value of existing investments, such as in the continuing development of IS VaVal, as well as serving to justify investment in PID integration and adoption. However, it is important to note that the benefits of PIDs and metadata go beyond efficiency.

2.2 PIDs support wider policy priorities

While efficiency gains can be measured in terms of time and money, other benefits that arise from comprehensive PID adoption are less easy to quantify, but are no less important. More complete, accurate, and timely information about research activities, outcomes, and impacts are critical to a number of priority areas for the Czech government and people, including the following examples.

2.2.1 Open research

PIDs are widely acknowledged as a fundamental building block for open research. PID registries contain much of the metadata that is valuable for open access (OA), and that helps support tracking and monitoring of progress towards OA targets and goals. For this reason, PIDs are a key component of the technical framework for OA policies, such as Plan S [10] or the European

Commission's guidance on access to scientific research, which states explicitly that "Member States should ensure that research funding institutions responsible for managing public research funding and academic institutions receiving public funding implement the policies and national action plans referred to in point 1 at national level in a coordinated way by... ensuring that publications resulting from public funding are easily identifiable by appropriate technical means, including through metadata attached to electronic versions of the research output and persistent identifiers" [11].

Open research, however, goes beyond access to publications, reaching back into the entire research lifecycle. This presents both challenges and opportunities.

At present, it is impossible to know how much research data is produced in Czech institutions; valuable data may be languishing on hard drives in desk drawers, or on old computers. For this reason, the National Strategy for Open Access to Scientific Information of the Czech Republic for 2017-2020 emphasised the importance of data being stored in, preserved by, and accessible through, digital repositories: "Open research data is, in particular, data in digital form originating from research projects (from experiments, investigations and measurements, including so-called metadata [data that provides information about other data] and details of data processing) available without restriction online to all potential users" [12].

While the systematic use of PIDs for datasets will enable a clear understanding of the volume, nature, and scope of the data assets being produced by Czech researchers, the policy refers to linking these datasets to the instruments etc. that were used in creating them. This is easily achieved using PIDs, which can be embedded in the metadata for the dataset. These connections from research outputs to equipment, people, funding, or projects are also vital for research integrity. The combination of open research practices and open PIDs provides a tremendous opportunity to improve insight into the impacts and achievements of national and international investments in Czech research.

2.2.2 Building a knowledge economy

The desire to build a strong knowledge economy in the Czech Republic lies at the heart of the RIS3 Strategy: "The long-term strategic vision formulates the basic direction of the development of the Czech Republic with an emphasis on the sphere of the knowledge economy and the transformation of the economy so that competitiveness based on innovation grows" [13].

At the same time, the RIS3 strategy acknowledges that "R&D&I management does not yet rely sufficiently on strategic intelligence, i.e. on strategic information on the state and dynamics of the development of the R&D&I system in the Czech Republic and its individual parts, on new trends and needs to which research should respond in terms of social relevance, as well as on the effects of implemented policy and measures" [3].

Strategic insight and evidence are essential if a strong knowledge economy is to be created for the long term. The national RDI strategy includes as an objective: "ensure strategic and evidence-based management of RDI" [4]. Many of the indicators of quality underpinning these strategic goals can be monitored most efficiently using PIDs (e.g. RORs for organisational affiliations for international partners, ORCID IDs to identify collaborators and to track global publications and venues, and so on).

Investments in centralised support for PIDs accelerate PID adoption and integration. In turn, improved PID coverage will deliver efficiencies that more than repay the costs of integration. Furthermore, beyond these savings, the use of PIDs will improve strategic insights into research activity and achievements, and can help to deliver top national priorities in a range of areas.

3 The Czech research landscape

3.1 Czech Information System for Research & Development (IS VaVal)

Great strides have been made in recent years in Czechia to unify research activity information reporting and collection in a publicly accessible and transparent manner. The national CRIS system Research, Development, and Innovation Information System, or Informační systém výzkumu, vývoje a inovací (IS VaVal) [14], is the public information system that collects, processes, uses, and provides information on research, development, and innovation supported by Czech public funding. The system comprises of four interconnected databases, covering:

- Programmes (CEA)
- Calls for proposals (VES)
- Awarded grants (CEP)
- Research outputs (RIV)

The CEA, VES, and CEP databases are populated by funders and by the IS VaVal operator, who input data into an application called RoP. To populate the RIV database, research activity data is reported from each of the publicly-funded research institutions, who enter their data through an application called VaVER. Batch XML files are created from that data and sent to each of the Czech funding agencies, who collate the research output data from all institutions that receive funding from them and consolidate it into new XML files. These are then sent to the IS VaVal operator, who uploads them to the database. The result is a publicly accessible resource that links programmes to funding calls, to awarded grants, and to the resulting research outputs.

3.2 The scale of research activity

The value of PIDs stems from the various use cases described in section 2. These include reducing administrative burden; enhancing automation; and improving data and metadata quality, timeliness, and completeness for decision-making at national, organisational, and individual levels. This analysis focuses on the immediate, direct cost and time savings associated with lessening the burden on researchers and research administrators, in particular by minimising the need for manual re-entry of metadata across multiple information systems for research publication, management, and reporting.

The cost of unnecessary manual data re-entry and the subsequent cost savings are dependent on the scale of activity and the number of entities and the extent of the metadata connecting them, including:

- Research institutions
- Research projects within institutions
- Funded grant awards
- Research publications
- Publication authorships

3.2.1 Unique identification of research institutions

The RIV database contains the names and unique IČO⁴, of institutions that report publications by their researchers. Currently, IČOs are not directly mapped to Research Organization Registry (ROR) IDs⁵, however, IS VaVal plans to implement ROR in 2025 [15]. In the meantime, mapping can be done by searching the ROR database for the names of institutions. Based on counting unique instances of IČOs in the RIV database for the period 2018-2022, we find 320 unique research-conducting organisations in Czechia that report publications through IS VaVal.

For the purpose of the cost-benefit analysis below, we focused on the 110 institutions targeted by the CARDS project. We know that 92% of research results in the RIV database are reported by 110 top institutions. In addition, not all the Czech research-conducting institutions will require their own PID integrations since they will benefit from several services with in-built support of PIDs (most of them currently in development within the Czech EOSC initiative [16]) such as the National Repository.

3.2.2 Estimating the number of research projects

Projects are an important part of research information management as they represent the work done within research institutions. However, there is little agreement on how to define, describe, or count projects, and different stakeholders understand projects differently. For example, funders often define projects as synonymous with awarded grants, but research projects within institutions may be unfunded, or funded by several grants. In our analysis, we define projects as discrete pieces of research work within institutions, as this is more relevant to how research activities at institutions are conducted.

Globally, research projects are poorly tracked. Information about them is often scattered within institutions in electronic laboratory notebooks, financial systems, and current research information systems (CRIS). The new Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)⁶ will address this issue by codifying projects as an entity with a defined metadata schema, which will be very valuable for research tracking and assessment in the future. For now, we assume that project numbers scale with levels of research funding. Previous estimates of the number of active projects in the United Kingdom (UK) [7] were scaled using published numbers for levels of research funding from OECD⁷. Using this approach, we estimate that Czechia has 9.5% the number of research projects as the UK, i.e., 4,754 active projects to be reported on, at any given time. Some of these projects may be multi-year activities, others may be much shorter. However, our estimate is not tied to the start or end dates,

⁴ Identifikační číslo osoby IČO is a unique eight-digit identification number in Czechia of a legal entity, a natural person doing business or an organizational unit of the state.

⁵ The Research Organization Registry (ROR) is a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organisations that is emerging as the *de facto* standard for organisation PIDs. For more information about ROR, see: <https://ror.org/>.

⁶ RAiD is unique identifier for research projects and activities, developed by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). It is rapidly gaining traction internationally and is backed by an ISO standard. For more information, see <https://raid.org/>.

ISO 23527:2022 Information and documentation – Research activity identifier (RAiD) [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Oct 11]. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/standard/75931.html>.

⁷ OECD data can be found here: <https://data.oecd.org/rd/gross-domestic-spending-on-r-d.htm>.

but is derived from comparing levels of funding with the benchmark assessment (levels of project activity in the UK).

Figure 1: Gross domestic spending in the United Kingdom and Czechia. This data was used as a relative measure of the size of the research environment to generate a scaling factor to estimate the number of projects.

3.2.3 The number of reported authorships

As described in section 3.1, the RIV database contains reports of publications resulting from research from Czech public funds. For each report, the institution lists the number of researchers at their institution associated with that publication. RIV contains a wide variety of output types, including patents, software, prototypes, and several others. However, for the purposes of our analysis, we have restricted ourselves to the following output types:

- Peer-reviewed journal articles
- Books
- Book chapters
- Proceedings

Not all entries in the RIV database have DOIs associated with them – for the period 2018-2022, approximately 66% of the 273,291 reports listed include DOIs. To estimate the number of publications represented in the data, therefore, we used DOIs where available; when no DOI was available, we used titles to deduplicate the institutional reports and uniquely identify publications.

It is obligatory to report publications resulting from Czech public funding to the RIV database, but it does not reliably include publications resulting from work that is either not funded, or funded by non-Czech funders, such as the European Union. If we only considered data from the RIV database, therefore, we would be undercounting the administrative burden faced by researchers and administrators. To partially correct for this, our analysis also includes publication data from the Digital Science Dimensions Database (Dimensions)⁸. Dimensions is a database of publications, grant

⁸ Daniel W. Hook, Simon J. Porter, and Christian Herzog, 'Dimensions: Building Context for Search and Evaluation', *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, vol. 3, p. 23, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2018.00023>.

awards, patents, researchers, and institutions that is built from a mix of both open and licensed proprietary data sources.

In order to reduce the risk of double counting publications, we constructed an API query using Dimensions Search Language (DSL) to extract publications by authors affiliated with Czech institutions that are linked to research grants funded by organisations outside of Czechia. For example, an article in the Dimensions data that was published by an author at Charles University and funded by the European Commission would be counted, but one by the same author, funded by the Czech Science Foundation, would not.

By combining both the RIV and Dimensions database, we estimate that there are approximately 67,000 publications in Czechia per year, as shown in figure 2. The final estimate is likely to be an undercount, because we were only able to include publications where there is an explicit link between the publication and a non-Czech funder from the Dimensions data. We were therefore unable to count publications resulting from unfunded work, or publications where the Dimensions data pipeline could not identify the funding source, for example, due to a poorly formatted acknowledgement.

Figure 2: By combining both the RIV and data about non-Czech funders from the Dimensions database, we estimate that there are approximately 67,000 publications in Czechia per year.

For our eventual analysis, we need not just the number of publications, but also the number of authorships, because the time and financial cost of article metadata re-entry is proportional to the number of authors that have to assert that they are associated with each publication. Fortunately, the design of RIV makes this calculation relatively straightforward, as each Czech institution reports authorships for each publication. For the Dimensions data, we parsed out authorships and affiliations, filtering out authors with no Czech affiliation.

Figure 3 shows the estimated number of authorships based on a combination of RIV and Dimensions data per year, broken down by institution; the most prolific 15 institutions are shown in separate colours. Since there is no direct cross-mapping of Dimensions IDs with IČO, we mapped both Dimensions IDs and institution names from the RIV data to RORs using the ROR API.

Figure 3: By combining both the RIV and data about non-Czech funders from the Dimensions database, and counting the number of authors affiliated with Czech institutions, we estimate approximately 149,000 authorships per year.

As can be seen from figure 3, averaging over the three years between 2020 and 2022 gives us a value of 148,992.

3.2.4 The number of reported grants

The CEP database contains records of awarded grants by Czech public funders to Czech research institutions. In order to get a more complete picture of Czech research grants, we combined data from CEP with data from the Digital Science Dimensions database, which explicitly includes data on EU-funded R&D projects encompassing Horizon Europe, H2020, and its predecessors, corresponding to the data in the CORDIS⁹ database.

⁹ More information about the CORDIS database can be found here: <https://cordis.europa.eu/>.

Figure 4: The number of grants received by Czech institutions based on data contained in the CEP database combined with data from the Dimensions database.

We combined grants data from CEP with data from Dimensions for grants awarded to Czech institutions from funders not based in Czechia. Averaging over the three years from 2020 to 2022, we estimate that 2,024 grants are awarded each year.

4 Cost-benefit analysis

The analysis used in this report is based on a methodology we developed to assess the sustainability of a programme to encourage PID adoption for Jisc in the UK [17]. It has since been applied in a similar context for Australia, in work funded by Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and Australian Access Federation (AAF) [2]; and for Ireland, in work funded by the National Open Research Forum [8] (see those reports for more information about the methodology). The calculations used in this analysis are presented in detail in the workbook in Appendix A.

In our analysis, we calculate the direct cost savings achieved when PID metadata registries are integrated into information systems by eliminating the manual rekeying of research activity information. These integrations would enable grants, projects, and publications to be uniquely identified, thereby eliminating challenges around deduplication when analysing research performance and activity. These three entities were used as the focus for this analysis as the metadata associated with them is widely re-used, enabling the quantification of benefits. PIDs for other entities associated with research, such as people or organisations, enable the accurate identification of relevant grants, publications etc. and the routing of information to institutional systems. As such, the benefits of these PIDs include enabling the metadata entry time savings set out in this report, as well as other kinds of process efficiency for which evidence was not available for this analysis.

In addition, information like titles, authors, affiliations, abstracts, dates, etc can be automatically populated into institutional, funder, and government information systems. We offset these savings against the costs of implementing PID integrations at 110 institutions targeted by the CARDS project. Finally, we present two scenarios, one in which institutions cover the full cost and effort of integration themselves, and one in which they are supported by the central PID support programme, hosted at NTK. In addition, we calculate the savings to date created by the ORCID and DataCite consortia that are supported by the CARDS project, by comparing the consortia costs to those that would be incurred by institutions if they were to become individual members.

4.1 Total potential cost savings

The estimates for the annual numbers of projects, grants, and authorships calculated in section 3.2 were used to calculate predicted cost savings. We multiplied the estimates for each of these three entities by an estimate of the number of times researchers and administrators enter information into various systems, based on our own previous surveys into academic research workflows [2]. Such systems include CRISs, internal reporting, repositories, financial systems, and others.

The total opportunity cost of all of these metadata re-entry events was calculated by multiplying them by the amount of time they take [17, 18] and by the fully costed average salaries and overhead for academic research staff and university administrators, based on data taken from the Average Earnings Information System (ISPV)¹⁰.

¹⁰ Data from the Average Earnings Information System (ISPV) can be downloaded here: <https://www.ispv.cz/cz/Vysledky-setreni/Aktualni.aspx>. Average salaries for Professionals in administration and organisational administration (ISCO 3343) and Teachers at universities and colleges (ISCO 2310) were used respectively.

Total potential sector savings							
	Number	# rekey events	# minutes / event	Time savings per year (person days)	Cost / author / minute		Financial savings per year
Publication metadata	148,992	3.1	6.73	6,476	8.58 CZK	- if research administrator	26,666,605 CZK
					10.45 CZK	- if researcher	32,482,306 CZK
					Average		29,574,456 CZK
Grant metadata	2,024	3.25	10	137	8.58 CZK	- if research administrator	564,315 CZK
					10.45 CZK	- if researcher	687,387 CZK
					Average		625,851 CZK
Project descriptions	4,754	6	10	594	8.58 CZK	- if research administrator	2,447,128 CZK
					10.45 CZK	- if researcher	2,980,821 CZK
					Average		2,713,975 CZK
Total potential annual savings from auto-feed of key metadata via API links:				7,207			32,914,281 CZK

Table 1: Total potential savings in both time and money if all publication, grant and project metadata were synchronised automatically into institutional information systems at research performing organisations in Czechia.

4.2 Institutional implementation costs

PID implementations must be financially sustainable for research institutions. Five priority PIDs necessary to capture and automate the transfer of research activity information between systems were identified in a multi-year international consultation [20] and further validated in subsequent academic research workflow analyses [21]:

- Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for funding grants of all kinds
- Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ORCID) IDs for people
- Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs) for projects
- Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers for organisations
- DOIs for outputs (especially articles and data)

We base our institutional implementation cost estimates on work done by Johnson et al [18], who estimated that an ORCID implementation takes approximately 40 person days. In that work, the total time burden included not just technical integration but also the creation of documentation, outreach, and educational efforts. In reality, for an institution implementing multiple PIDs, there would be some work from each integration that would be reused and some lessons that would be learned, particularly around staff training and communication. In addition, some integrations would be lighter-weight than ORCID. For example, for most institutions, integrating with ROR (which is a centrally curated database of institutions) would only require the ability to read data from the ROR registry; as opposed to the complexity of integrating with ORCID (which is updated by multiple stakeholders, including end-users). We therefore estimate that integration of all five priority PIDs would cost four times as much as a single ORCID integration. We spread implementation costs over five years and, again, we took salary data from the ISPV, averaging it over a number of relevant technical roles (see Appendix A for more information).

As mentioned previously, we present two scenarios – one in which we calculate the costs for PID implementations without support from the NTK PIDs programme, and one with that support. The CARDS project plays a valuable role in reducing implementation costs at the institutional level through outreach, education, and knowledge-sharing. To account for this positive effect at the institutional level we have assumed that, with support from a national service, the time taken to integrate the five priority PIDs would be reduced to just twice as long as a single ORCID integration.

4.3 Costs of the national PIDs support programme

The costs of the CARDS project itself must also be considered; it covers the Czech ORCID and DataCite consortia, as well as a range of support and community services. When considering the implementation costs, we therefore looked at the cost of staff needed to provide the support services including a coordinator, technical community manager, engagement and outreach managers, and legal and other support staff.

We have not included the subscription costs of the consortia themselves, as those are considered separately when we look at consortia savings.

4.4 Target levels of adoption

PIDs are network entities – because they facilitate information-sharing, the more organisations that make use of PID integrations, the more valuable those integrations are to each organisation, so the fractional economic benefit is not linearly dependent on the number of PID integrations. Instead, if there are few institutional integrations, the incremental benefit for each new integration is low; as the network of institutions that have integrations grow, the incremental benefit to new integrators increases until it eventually plateaus. To model the benefit as PID adoption increases, we applied a logistic function, which is a common method used to model such effects [22].

4.4.1 Understanding PID adoption

PID adoption here refers to the use of PIDs and metadata in systems to save time and effort by reusing metadata and automating processes. Adoption relies on two interdependent factors: PID coverage and PID integrations.

PID coverage is vital to encourage PID integrations. If only 5% of researchers have an ORCID ID, there is very little incentive to use resources to integrate the ORCID API into a system. The greater the level of PID coverage, the higher the potential value of a PID integration. PID integrations enable the benefits of PIDs to be delivered, allowing metadata to be reused and, therefore, saving researchers and administrators time and money.

PID coverage

There are two ways that coverage can be assessed and evaluated:

1. Where the total number of instances of a given entity can be established (e.g. the number of publications or grants), we can compare that total with the number of PIDs in the relevant registry or registries. This measure of PID coverage can then be expressed as a percentage of the total number of known entities, e.g., 90% of Czech research organisations have a ROR, and a recent analysis based on RIV data suggested that ORCID adoption is close to 60% among researchers in the Czech Republic [23].
2. If this information is not available (e.g. we do not have reliable data on the total number of datasets at a given time), we can, instead, track changes in the number of PIDs registered for each entity over time, by measuring the absolute number registered and the rates of registration per year for each.

This information can then be used to help to set realistic targets for improvements in coverage. For example, given that current ORCID adoption is already at 60%, a target of 80% seems achievable. Targets for PID coverage when the total number of entities is not known will need to be set for each class of entity based on the availability of PIDs for that entity, the current number of PIDs registered for those entities, and the scale of effort or change required to implement those PIDs widely.

PID integrations

A PID integration is when a software instance has an active connection to a PID registry API and is reading metadata from the registry, adding metadata to records, or both. Integration levels are

measured by counting the number of active API connections and the scope of their use at the time of investigation.

4.4.2 Setting adoption targets

We do not currently have access to data to evaluate the number and scope of PID integrations. The only reliable method that has been developed for assessing integrations is to use surveys. This approach is a proven method of establishing levels of PID integration and usage, and has been developed and refined over projects led by OCLC and EuroCRIS [24], and by the MoreBrains teams for the UK [25] and Ireland [26].

This phase of our work has been focused on PID coverage, but a survey will be needed in future phases, in order to measure the levels of PID integrations. If the survey is run more than once, it can be used to measure change in these levels and therefore progress towards adoption targets.

Table 2 shows the net aggregate savings across all Czech research institutions of implementing the five priority PIDs. Two scenarios are presented. In the first, the net savings from section 4.1 are offset by the cost of implementation at every one of the 110 institutions without the support of the national program funded by the CARDS project. In this case, the savings from reduced data rekeying are adequate to cover implementation costs at a level just below 60% adoption. At 80% adoption, savings are 7,870,137 CZK per year. In the second scenario, with support from the CARDS project, savings exceed costs at an adoption level of between 50% and 55%; at 80% adoption, savings reach 12,245,728 CZK.

As noted above, successful PID adoption depends on coverage being high enough to incentivise integrations, and integrations reaching a level that enables metadata reuse at a large scale. Given that 55% of possible metadata reuse needs to be delivered to enable savings to exceed investments in PID integrations and support services, we would suggest that a target be set for integrations of at least that amount, adjusted for coverage levels.

The benefits of PID adoption can be realised if a high enough percentage of research activity in Czech institutions can be captured in systems with active PID integrations, and enough of the inputs and outputs of that research activity have PIDs. Targeting PID integrations in institutions that produce the most research activity will achieve the target most efficiently, but risks leaving smaller or less research intensive organisations behind. For these, it may make sense to ensure that they can benefit from PID integrations by focusing on integrations in shared systems that can generate efficiencies for their researchers and administrators.

If our recommended target of 80% coverage for priority PIDs is achieved, then an integration target of 68.75% would be needed to deliver 55% adoption (80% of 68.75 being 55). This approach, as noted above, implies weighting the contribution of each integration to the target according to the volume of research activity recorded in the information systems that are integrating PIDs. Without accurate and up-to-date information on current levels of institutional adoption, it is not possible to set a realistic target or timelines for institutional adoption, so we recommend that this target be re-assessed with the input of the survey planned for 2025. As integration plans can take several years and require longer term focus and commitment, we would also suggest incorporating agreed targets into future national strategies and planning documents.

If central services can provide access to PID benefits to a large group of organisations, then the target levels for institutional adoption could be lower. This balance will need to be determined based on the levels of research activity at the organisations implementing PIDs and at those using central services.

Net savings based on levels of adoption								
Adoption levels	0%	20%	40%	50%	55%	60%	80%	90%
Effective benefit (considering adoption curve)	0.0%	4.7%	26.9%	50.0%	62.2%	73.1%	95.3%	98.2%
Total sector time savings in person-days every year	0	342	1938	3604	4486	5269	6865	7078
Cost savings (benefit) every year	-	1,560,989 CZK	8,852,014 CZK	16,457,141 CZK	20,487,802 CZK	24,062,268 CZK	31,353,293 CZK	32,322,278 CZK
Scenario 1: With no central support from NTK PID programme								
Cost of Implementation /year across all institutions	(23,483,156 CZK)							
Net savings offset by costs	(23,483,156 CZK) (21,922,167 CZK) (14,631,142 CZK) (7,026,015 CZK) (2,995,354 CZK) 579,112 CZK 7,870,137 CZK 8,839,122 CZK							
Scenario 2: With central support from NTK PID programme								
Cost of Implementation /year across all institutions	(11,741,578 CZK)							
Cost of NTK PID Programme	(7,365,987 CZK)							
Net savings offset by costs	(19,107,565 CZK) (17,546,576 CZK) (10,255,551 CZK) (2,650,424 CZK) 1,380,237 CZK 4,954,703 CZK 12,245,728 CZK 13,214,713 CZK							

Table 2: The aggregate net cost and/or benefit of universal adoption of five priority PIDs at Czech institutions. With support from a central PID service provided by NTK, PID integrations become self-funding at between 50 and 55% adoption.

4.5 Savings as a result of the national PID consortia

In addition to the cost savings generated by PIDs and the support services provided by the CARDS project, the ORCID and DataCite consortia, started as part of the NTK PIDs support programme and led by NTK, also provide cost savings. Table 3 shows the costs that would be incurred by the 11 DataCite consortium members and 24 ORCID consortium members if they were individual members¹¹. We compare these costs to the consortia fees and find that, at current membership levels, these two consortia save Czech institutions 3,050,240 CZK annually.

Net savings due to consortia membership				
National Consortium	Number of institutions	Cost per institution	Cost for all institutions	
Costs of individual memberships				
DataCite	11	(50,000 CZK)	(550,000 CZK)	
ORCID	24	(207,000 CZK)	(4,968,000 CZK)	
Total costs			(5,518,000 CZK)	
Costs of consortium membership				
DataCite	N/A	N/A	(50,000 CZK)	
ORCID	24	(100,740 CZK)	(2,417,760 CZK)	
Total costs			(2,467,760 CZK)	
Savings per year created by both consortia			3,050,240 CZK	

Table 3: Savings to date as a result of both the DataCite and ORCID consortia funded by the CARDS project. Note that savings will increase as the number of member institutions increases.

¹¹ There were 11 members of the DataCite consortium and 24 members of the ORCID consortium at the time of writing (December 2024). As more institutions join the consortia, the annual savings will increase.

5 Conclusions

It is clear from our analysis that providing support for PID adoption in Czech institutions will deliver a significant return on investment. By expanding consortium memberships, technical support, and community outreach and education, the central national support for PIDs (coordinated by NTK as part of the CARDS project) and PID adoption/services available in the National Data Infrastructure will be essential to maximising these returns, and to delivering them on the shortest possible time scale.

We have reasonable estimates of the current levels of PID coverage for some entities (organisations and people, for example). We strongly recommend undertaking follow-up research to survey number and scope of current and planned PID integrations within Czech institutions, and to evaluate the coverage of Czech research entities within PID registries. This will establish a baseline of PID adoption and enable ongoing assessment of progress.

The potential overall financial savings from metadata re-use and process automation are higher than the financial costs of PID integrations and support. Our modelling indicates that, with PID adoption at 55%, the net savings will be 1,380,237 CZK. As adoption rises, the net savings also rise to 13,214,713 CZK at 90% PID adoption. These annual financial savings are generated by savings in the time spent on administrative tasks, and could easily exceed the 7,207 person days per year. This makes the goal of increasing PID adoption critical to meeting the Czech policy priorities of reducing administrative burden and enhancing the knowledge economy, as set out in the RIS3 [\[27\]](#) and RDI [\[4\]](#) strategies. With the results of our analysis in mind, we recommend setting a target of 80% coverage across all five priority PIDs reinforced with a target of PID integrations in at least 60% of institutional research information systems (calculated either in absolute terms – number of systems – or in terms of systems containing 60% of the overall research information), as this would be sufficient to guarantee a return on investment.

In addition, increasing the coverage of PIDs for grants, outputs, organisations, people, and projects will enable significant improvements in the understanding of research activity and impacts. Being able to better discover and quantify research outputs will enable strategic insights, such as enabling the identification of trends in research collaboration or emerging areas of expertise on innovative new topics, thereby supporting better investment and improved social and economic impact.

Increasing the visibility of Czech research in global PID registries will also help to deliver key national policy goals. This includes the R&D strategy goals to increase the quality and international excellence of research and development in the Czech Republic, to increase the openness and attractiveness of the Czech Republic for international research and development, and to intensify the integration of the Czech Republic's research and development into the European Research Area. Enhancing the discovery and reach of Czech research will also maximise its impact, helping to serve the RIS3 strategy's goal to increase the quality and social relevance of public research.

The most complete and comprehensive PID adoption possible should therefore be the goal in subsequent work of stakeholders in the Czech research ecosystem, including all institutions (large and small), as well as funders, and the services used by Czech researchers. We recommend that, alongside the central PID support work, PIDs should also be implemented in shared national systems, such as IS VaVal, National Repository, and other national systems and services, mainly

those planned to be built within the Czech EOSC initiative. This will ensure that smaller organisations, those that lack the technical capacity and those with a low level of research activity, can also benefit from PIDs directly, share information about their activities more widely, and ensure that their contributions to the growth of the Czech knowledge economy are efficient and effective.

To support this endeavour, we recommend undertaking additional research to identify keystone systems in which research information is aggregated (such as funder grant applications, reporting platforms, etc.) and targeting them for priority PID integrations. This will both increase the volume of metadata available for re-use via PID registries and also enhance the effectiveness of shared services. Good progress has already been made in this space with the establishment of the DataCite and ORCID consortia, and the planned ROR integrations.

Even allowing for the conservative assumptions used throughout this analysis, it is clear that the benefits of PID adoption in Czechia are significant. The real-world benefits are likely to exceed the levels estimated in this report, but will require targeted, strategic investment, and focused support to be realised. A mixed approach that includes central services, longer-term technical support, community education, and engagement will support an equitable and efficient rollout of PIDs in Czechia. This should be underpinned by robust evidence of adoption levels and current information-gathering burdens or inefficiencies in order to accurately target activities at the points of greatest need or potential impact, and to maximise the reach and scale of the Czech PID network.

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Appendix A – Cost-benefit calculation

See separate file - Appendix A – Cost benefit calculation, <https://doi.org/10.48813/g69y-mh46>.

Appendix B - Data Sources

7.1 IS VaVal

Data from the two databases (RIV - Research outputs, CEP - Awarded grants) was provided directly by Alexandr Kuchynka at NTK in the form of UTF-8 encoded CSV and XLSX files.

7.2 Digital Science Dimensions

Data from Dimensions was obtained under license via its API. Documentation can be found here: <https://www.dimensions.ai/resources/api-documentation>. The Dimensions API uses a custom query language called Dimensions Search Language (DSL), the specific queries used for this analysis are shown below:

Publications with authors from Czech institutions, funded by non-Czech funders

The Dimensions API is limited to 50,000 results per query and 1,000 results per page. To ensure compliance with those limits, data for each year was queried separately and results were downloaded 1,000 records at a time.

For example, the first page of results for 2018, were requested using the following DSL query.

```
search publications
where research_org_countries.id="CZ"
not funder_countries.id ~ "CZ"
and year = 2018
return publications[basics+doi+funders]
limit 1000 skip 0
```

Awarded research grants to Czech institutions, funded by non-Czech funders

The numbers of grants for the years 2018 - 2022 was fewer than 50,000 and did not require a separate query for each year. Below is the DSL query used for the first page of results.

```
search grants
where research_org_countries.id="CZ"
and start_year in [2018:2022]
and research_org_types~"Education"
not funder_org_countries.id="CZ"
return grants[basics+funder_orgs+research_orgs+research_org_types]
limit 1000 skip 0
```

As with all databases, data in IS VaVal and Dimensions may be revised and improved over time and as better data becomes available. In the interests of reproducibility, the script used to analyse the Dimensions data was run three times over a one-week period from 18-25 November 2024.

7.3 ROR

ROR data is openly available through its API. Documentation can be found here:

<https://ror.readme.io/>.

ROR IDs were obtained based on either GRID IDs or institution names using a simple search query. URL encoding is required. For example, the ROR ID for the Czech Technical University in Prague can be obtained from the JSON data structure returned by the following URL.

```
https://api.ror.org/organizations?query=%22%C4%8Cesk%C3%A9%20vysok%C3%A9%20u%C4%8Den%C3%AD%20technick%C3%A9%20v%20Praze%22
```